

Single-chip Interband Cascade DFB laser with Extended Tuning Range

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Abstract—We report the operation of an interband cascade-based DFB laser in the mid-IR. The device operates single-mode from 78 to 160 K, with up to 10 nm of current tuning and quasi-continuous tuning of 26 nm by also varying temperature.

Midwave-infrared (mid-IR) lasers in the wavelength range of 3 – 4 μm are needed for a number of applications including chemical sensing, IR countermeasures, and free-space communications. At present, the most promising source for this wavelength range is the interband cascade laser (ICL). Recent ICLs have demonstrated cw operation up to 269 K [1] with maximum CW output power of 200 mW per facet at 78 K [2] and wallplug efficiencies of 27% [3]. In addition to efficient cw operation, some of the mentioned applications also require single mode output. We report here the operation of a DFB ICL around 3.4 μm with a quasi-continuous tuning range of 26 nm. The structure was grown via molecular beam epitaxy at NRL on an *n*-GaSb substrate. From the substrate, a 3.5 μm InAs/AlSb superlattice *n*-cladding was grown followed by a 0.3 μm *n*-GaSb separate confinement heterostructure layer. Then the 5-stage interband cascade active region, an upper 0.3 μm thick InAs/AlSb superlattice *n*-cladding region, and a highly doped InAs cap layer were grown. Narrow ridges 10 μm wide were formed using contact lithography and chemical etching. The topography was smoothed by spinning on a flowable oxide layer. The 1st-order grating pattern was written using e-beam lithography, followed by e-beam deposition of 100 nm of germanium and subsequent lift-off. To eliminate higher-order lateral modes and enhance DFB coupling, a 300 nm thick silicon rib was sputter deposited on top of the 10 μm wide ridge. An SiO₂ layer was sputtered and lifted off to form a contact region to the top of the ridge. Finally, a Ag/Ti/Pt/Au metallization was e-beam evaporated over the ridge, contacting the regions outside of the silicon rib.

The devices were thinned to 170 μm , metallized on the backside with Ag/Cr/Sn/Pt/Au, annealed at 300°C for 1 minute, and cleaved to form laser cavities. For testing, the laser bars were mounted epitaxial side up and HR/AR facet coatings were deposited.

Four grating periods were fabricated: 492, 496, 500 and 504 nm. The resulting devices lased between 3.37 and 3.45 μm , as shown in Fig. 1. The device with a grating period of 496 nm, silicon rib width of 4 μm and cavity length of 670 μm lased single mode for all applied currents and temperatures from 78 to 160 K, with an SMSR exceeding 30 dB for high currents (Fig. 2). As shown in Fig. 3, the peak measured output power for temperatures up to 120 K is greater than 7 mW. The laser tuned over 21 nm by varying the temperature with an applied bias of 65 mA. By varying the injected power density, the laser tunes over 10 nm at temperatures from 78 to 120 K. Through a combination of temperature and current injection variation, the wavelength can be tuned quasi-continuously over 26 nm as shown in Fig. 4.

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Fig. 1: Lasing spectra at $T = 120\text{ K}$ and $I = 50\text{ mA}$ for four different grating periods: 492, 496, 500, and 504 nm.

Fig. 3: CW output power versus injection current at various temperatures.

Fig. 2: Lasing spectrum at 78 K and an applied current of 140 mA showing greater than 30 dB of SMSR.

Fig. 4: Wavelength tuning with injected power for three cryostat temperatures.